

Ten Simple Rules for Researchers: Upskilling for a Rapidly Evolving Workforce

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Introduction

As we enter the fourth research paradigm, as evidenced by rapid advancements in the scientific methodology involving data-intensive practices (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2024; Vincent-Lancrin, 2006, Rapport & Braithwaite, 2018), upskilling the next generation of researchers has become pivotal.

If you are a researcher, you will likely assist others in learning new skills, from computational tools to different data analysis methods. This knowledge transfer often happens organically and informally through mentorship and collegiality, but a more structured approach would be vastly beneficial and impactful to those needing to upskill. When organizing a skills event for others, you may require guidance on where to begin.

Short-format training (SFT) provides an efficient medium to meet the demands of a fast-evolving workforce. It allows researchers to stay informed and identify opportunities for rapid and ongoing skill enhancement. An SFT refers to a non-formal workshop, short course, boot camp, or similar, that teaches skills and knowledge over a brief period, usually hours, days, or weeks. A study led by Williams et al, called to make SFT more reliable, effective, inclusive, and career-spanning in the face of rapid technological changes.

The following recommendations were inspired by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) Digital Research Skills Summit 2023, that brought together Researchers, Learning Designers, Skills Trainers, and Librarians in productive discussions on how to run effective researcher skills training.

We have curated our ten simple rules into a streamlined workflow to assist in developing SFT (see [Figure 1](#)). These rules outline how to think about skills learning for researchers, plan training sessions, and efficiently maximize learning. We offer recommendations on how to design and develop learner-centered training programs (Rules [1](#) and [2](#)), foster outreach, and connect with trainer communities (Rules [3](#) and [4](#)). We then provide tips to manage and optimize training (Rules [5](#), [6](#), and [7](#)), and conclude with valuable insights on preparing for uncertainty and the importance of post-training operations and continued learning (Rules [8](#), [9](#), and [10](#)).

Figure 1: The basic steps of short format training (SFT) development.

Rule 1: Be learner-centered

A learner-centered training design considers the uniqueness of each learner and enables the trainer to play an impactful role in equipping individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary for success in their professional endeavors, ensuring equitable educational opportunities for all.

Learner diversity is a multifaceted and essential aspect of education and training. It encompasses a variety of backgrounds, cultural experiences, learning styles, abilities, and motivations. Recognizing and embracing this diversity is not just a moral imperative, it is also a fundamental pedagogical principle. It acknowledges that every learner brings unique strengths and challenges to the learning environment, making the educational experience richer and more dynamic. By valuing and accommodating this diversity, educators and trainers can create inclusive, authentic, and equitable learning spaces where all individuals have the opportunity to thrive and reach their full potential. This fosters an environment that celebrates the richness of human experiences and promotes learning outcomes that are both meaningful and impactful. The ultimate goal is to empower learners to become active participants in their learning process, and this is easier when learning experiences are authentic and relevant to the learner.

Implementing learner-centered learning design for SFT involves a structured approach that considers both the learner's perspective and the course objectives (Biggs & Tang, 2011; Fink, 2013; Mctighe & Wiggins, 2013; Wiggins & McTighe, 2006). The following seven steps summarize this structured approach.

- **Define the overall goal.** Start with the end in mind. What should learners be able to achieve by the end of the training?
- **Define the audience** and characteristics of learners. Understand what appeals to them, their backgrounds, and their motivations.
- **Define learning delivery modality.** With technology advancements, learners can choose their learning experience: in-person, online, hybrid, blended, self-paced eLearning, mobile learning, or virtual classrooms. See [Figure 2](#) for various delivery modalities for SFT.
- **Brainstorm ideas.** Collaborate with learners, subject matter experts, and learning specialists to understand what should be covered, how to do it, what will not be included, and to anticipate problems or misconceptions. Draw concept maps to visualize the course structure.
- **Develop challenges** that allow learners to practice. Challenges serve as benchmarks for learners and trainers to gauge progress and identify areas needing further attention.
- **Motivate learners** by organizing course content to align with their motivations. Demonstrating real-world relevance and applicability enhances learner engagement and success.

- **Write a course description** to help the target audience understand if the course is suitable for them.

Using a learner-centered approach involves tailoring the experience to diverse learners' individual needs and preferences, rather than following a one-size-fits-all approach. Keep the learners at the center of the learning process. A successful learning design prioritizes the individual needs and preferences of learners while aligning course content with their motivations and real-world applications. It is about fostering active participation, personalization, and inclusivity, ultimately resulting in more effective skills training.

Figure 2: Modes for delivering short format training (SFT).

Rule 2: Use frameworks

Training and learning frameworks offer varied and structured methods to assist learners to develop an understanding of the specific skills they need, give perspective on their current skill level, and guide learners on when and how to effectively apply the skills and knowledge they acquire (Ambrose et al., 2010).

Frameworks are relevant to trainer activity in a range of ways, offering a multifaceted approach to enhance learner experience. They provide trainers with an evidence-based process aligning learning goals with activities and structures to create motivating and stable environments for impactful learning. From an operational perspective, frameworks serve to ensure learners have the appropriate skills to succeed in their roles. They guide learners into roles where their existing skills can be leveraged, act as strategic tools to help learners and organizations pinpoint and address existing skills gaps, facilitate interconnections and linkages across diverse skills frameworks, and ensure the usage of a consistent terminology (taxonomy) underpinning a coordinated skills system (Ambrose et al., 2010).

From a learner perspective, frameworks create and identify structured training pathways and instill confidence that the skills they are acquiring are valuable and progress to future skills (Ambrose et al., 2010). A framework is a way for learners to reach a shared understanding of what a skill, competency, or ability refers to and how particular skills relate to other skills. They connect terms for skills in a taxonomic manner so users of the framework can understand what specific terms are encompassed by more general terms and vice versa.

Organizations with experience and a level of responsibility for providing training may create frameworks to ensure training occurs in a structured, progressive, and effective manner. Frameworks may cover a national or geographic area (Jobs and Skills Australia, 2023; SkillsFuture Singapore, 2023); be international and cover a broad range of occupational domains and disciplines (SFIA Foundation, 2023); focus on general fundamental employability skills (Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, 2022); or be for narrowly defined highly-skilled populations (Engineering Education Australia, 2024; Unsworth et al, 2022). Skills underpin all work and impact the types of work people perform and how successfully they perform it. As there is no single all-encompassing framework, many have overlapping areas and interconnected components.

Established frameworks provide a range of structured and tested approaches that can be used when developing training. For instance, the Skills Framework for the Information Age (SFIA Foundation, 2023) and the Australian Core Skills Framework (Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, 2022) include recommendations for applying frameworks:

- assess and benchmark individual skills performance,

- describe and identify skills and knowledge needs (skills gaps) relevant to the role,
 - organization and sector,
- create career-tailored approaches to training, teaching, and learning,
- and align curriculum to organizational/sector needs for improving employability.

When applied within the workforce, the flow of training development starts through the identification of role profiles (or personas) to determine skills and knowledge needs, as well as competencies to assess the application of skills. From this, skills gaps can be determined and will inform the development of the learning pathway for SFT (see [Figure 3](#)).

Figure 3: Framework development flow chart.

Rule 3: Harness existing resources and expertise

The key to efficiently upskilling researchers in a rapidly evolving workforce is to tap into available resources and expertise. Leverage the knowledge, tools, training materials, and talents already available to enhance your training capabilities and effectiveness. Researching existing resources forms part of training preparation and saves time and effort.

Furthermore, developing and leveraging relationships with external training organizations facilitates collaborations and partnerships focused on training requirements, enabling the delegation of specialized tasks tailored to expertise. Using external facilitators allows in-house expertise and resources to be redirected. Consultants or external organizations may deliver specialist skills that could not be provided in-house or to smaller cohorts. Universities and research organizations may also have sectoral training events available to their researchers and postgraduate students focusing specifically on the digital skills required by a cohort.

We highlight two case studies where existing resources and external relationships have been cultivated and leveraged to develop, share, and deliver SFT.

Case study: DReSA

Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) is a skills and training registry created through a partnership between the ARDC, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, and 12 other research skills training providers (Digital Research Skills Australasia, 2024b). It provides a free online space where researchers can connect with trainers in Australasia and discover digital research training events, resources, and providers to develop SFT.

DReSA is a gateway for researchers providing training to leverage relationships with experienced trainers online and to access and share training resources.

To ensure DReSA comprehensively covers skills offerings for an evolving workforce, trainers and training providers are invited to create an account and register their resources. DReSA is still developing and expanding its listing of trainers, courses, and training organizations. As these mature, it provides a platform for trainers to connect and collaborate on courses and materials to upskill the next generation of digital researchers.

Case study: ResBaz

The Research Bazaar (ResBaz) is a face-to-face, international festival promoting digital literacy at the center of modern research (ResBaz, 2016). Since 2015, events have been held annually at university campuses globally. Festivals are held over multiple days, such as at ResBaz Queensland 2023 (“Research Bazaar Queensland,” 2023), a three-day intensive conference.

Existing relationships among digital skills trainers are leveraged to organize these events. Researchers come together to upskill in ‘next-generation digital research tools and skills’. The event organization and learning style accommodate researchers across diverse disciplines, fostering learning, camaraderie, and exchange of knowledge and skills. Collaborative face-to-face interactions create and nurture external relationships.

ResBaz events provide a supportive environment for researchers at all career stages, encouraging community-based learning. An introductory level of practical knowledge combined with networking opportunities fosters an inquiry-based learning approach. This facilitates the development of advanced skills tailored to researchers’ discipline, methodology, and research questions. An outcome of ResBaz is fostering and developing relationships within research communities.

Rule 4: Connect with trainer communities

Engaging with trainer communities is a great way to learn and understand the underpinnings of successful SFT, and to avoid training in isolation. A supportive and inclusive culture will enable you to align learning needs, common goals, and mindsets (Wenger & Snyder, 2000).

Strong outreach and community infrastructure are essential to supporting trainer uplift. They facilitate peer-to-peer supported learning and sharing of ideas and feedback, which can support succession planning ([Rule 8](#)). In a rapidly evolving workforce, connecting with communities that focus on digital training delivery will ensure you stay up-to-date with training best practices.

The Carpentries and RLadies are examples of training communities focused on digital upskilling that can be engaged for advice on SFT development.

Case study: The Carpentries

The Carpentries is a fiscally sponsored project of Community Initiatives with the purpose of “teach[ing] foundational coding and data science skills to researchers worldwide” (The Carpentries, 2024). The global community shares a mission to teach foundational computational and data science skills for conducting efficient, open, and reproducible research.

The community consists of experienced instructors, local champions, and education specialists who inspire and prepare new instructors (who are certified to run Carpentries workshops). They aim to spread data literacy and programmatic skills locally and globally by actively upskilling the instructional and technical skills of the instructor community. They foster an active and inclusive community by collaboratively developing openly-available lessons and delivering SFT using evidence-based teaching practices.

The Carpentries enthusiastically work as a team to maintain and teach the Instructor Training Curriculum (Word et al., 2021), and host teaching demonstration sessions to provide vital feedback to new instructors.

Case study: RLadies

RLadies is a global organization promoting gender diversity and inclusivity within the R programming community (<https://rladies.org>). Founded on the principle of empowering women and gender minorities, RLadies advocates for equity and representation in R programming by providing a space for underrepresented groups.

The organization provides educational resources, networking opportunities, mentorship, and training sessions, empowering members to excel in their careers and contribute meaningfully to the R community.

They embrace a collaborative approach to learning and knowledge sharing. Members share resources, tips, and best practices, fostering a culture of mutual support and growth. RLadies provides opportunities for organizers and members to enhance their teaching skills, expand their technical knowledge, and build their professional networks.

There are over 220 chapters (and growing) running globally, and an active online community. Anyone interested can join the community Slack channel (<https://rladies.org/form/community-slack>), and attend online and in-person events for support with SFT development for digital skill training.

Rule 5: Systematically manage logistics

When designing and delivering SFT the focus is often on content, while the management of administrative systems and logistics can be overlooked. Regardless of the size of the training, utilizing scheduling and registration systems can reduce the administrative burden pre- and post-training (especially if systems are integrated), allowing the trainer to focus on the learners and content.

Systematic methods of cataloging delivered training allow trend identification, evaluation of strategy effectiveness, and the direction of resources based on demand. This can also inform future modes of learning (see [rule 1](#)) and assist with the preparation to scale training (see [rule 9](#)) (Gašević et al., 2015; Greller & Drachsler, 2012).

To effectively manage SFT and determine how it will be delivered, it is helpful to consider:

- **Systems compatibility and integration:** Verify the platforms are compatible with your organization's systems. Determine whether enterprise versions of the platforms are available, and if integration of systems is available. For example, formatting your training resource for future sharing on DReSA will make it more discoverable without the administration hassle often associated with the process.
- **Requisite skills and knowledge:** Recognize the background skills and knowledge learners require to participate in the training. This also includes software needed before training commences or if learners need assistance to install software. Consider demonstrating or providing resources to enable participants to navigate the platform and tools used consistent with learner-centered training (see [Rule 1](#)).
- **Communicating with registrants:** Decide how to update learners on training details. Some registration systems allow emails to be sent to registrants.
- **Accessibility:** Consider whether the systems are universally accessible, and what system functionalities can support learners with additional needs.
- **Training evaluation:** Determine how learners provide training feedback and how easy it is to extract training evaluation data in the preferred format.

The above information can be captured using:

- **Scheduling systems:** The purpose of this system is to catalog all scheduled training activities at each institution/organization. Check with your organization to see what scheduling systems are used. This system should capture information about the
 - Name of the course (course code, title).
 - Date and time of a scheduled course (date, start and end time, time zone).

- Room booking details (if in person) or online platform details (e.g. Zoom link).
- Capacity (max number of registrants).
- Trainers' details (names, biographies, and contact information).
- **Registration systems:** This system should capture all the details about the training and information about registrants. There should also be options to capture user feedback pre- and post-training. Examples of registration systems include Eventbrite and Whova, but you can also use online forms or spreadsheets to track attendance. These should include:
 - Course information:
 - Title
 - Short Summary
 - Description
 - About the course
 - Learning Objectives
 - Prerequisites
 - Organizer
 - Date
 - Start and End Time
 - Time Zone
 - Picture (if applicable)
 - Participants information:
 - Full Name
 - Email
 - Institution
 - Faculty
 - School
 - Field Of Research (FOR) code
 - Role/Position
 - How did you hear about the course?
 - What other courses would you be interested in attending?
 - Why are you interested in this course?
 - Any acknowledgment (if applicable)
 - Would like to receive a Certificate of Attendance (yes/no) (if applicable)

Consideration of the above points, alongside data captured from participants, can determine the most appropriate mode for learners (see [Figure 2](#)).

Rule 6: Engage learners

As a training event approaches, the purpose of communication with learners switches from encouraging attendance to informing and preparing them for the learning experience. Maintaining interest and excitement by sending reminders, pre-work, expectations and sneak peeks (using the information gathered from the scheduling and registration platforms mentioned in [Rule 5](#)) increases retention (Miller, 2017; Sanders et al., 2019).

Once training commences, communication with learners is crucial to retain interest and transfer knowledge and skills to ensure maximum value and participation. This can be managed using the systems highlighted in [Rule 5](#). Trainers may enlist a variety of touchpoints in different modalities to reach learners:

- daily summaries for multi-day training,
- links to recordings and resources as needed,
- continuous access to systems and resources if required,
- availability of organizers and trainers for questions,
- information about upcoming sessions and agenda updates,
- opportunities for networking and feedback.

An impactful trainer keeps learners engaged through several pedagogical techniques within the classroom. The Carpentries' Instructor Training Curriculum (Word et al., 2021) teaches the following strategies for instructors to employ in workshops:

- Trainer as motivator: Share the benefits of what learners will learn, and confidence in their ability to employ these skills.
- Align learning objectives that resonate with audiences; for instance using 'authentic tasks', which are real-world activities/problems they may encounter in their everyday lives or professional contexts
- Prepare to use formative assessment to track learner progress
- Seek feedback from learners and act on it throughout the workshop
- Avoid demotivating learners by using dismissive language.

Allocate time for participants to interact and network with their colleagues by incorporating purposeful introductions at the start of training. This can promote collaboration, encourage idea exchange, and establish valuable connections. Training is not complete once the session has been delivered. Learners may have questions about content from the training and may need a few weeks to process what they learned. From the trainer's perspective, following up with learners can help obtain valuable feedback about the training and delivery for future improvements (Miller, 2017) ([Rule 7](#)). Providing feedback can be confronting for some people so assure them that it is confidential and anonymous.

Rule 7: Assess and Evaluate

Assessment is the measure of a learner's skills and knowledge (Suskie, 2009), while evaluation is the systematic process of collecting information and using it to improve future training (Kreber et al., 2001). Both are important indicators of learner performance and program efficacy, as they provide measurable observation.

What is delivered is not always received how trainers intended. It is important to prompt learners to reflect on their learning. Obtaining feedback from learners through formative assessment on the day helps to create impactful SFT that resonates. Consequently, learners may find SFT more relevant as it aligns with their needs and experiences. Planning the type of assessment and, subsequently, evaluation strategies to embed in training facilitates this process.

In SFT, self-assessment questions are frequently used: pre-training surveys, live quizzes, multiple-choice questions, and check-out questions at the end of a session. Using them flexibly throughout training helps gauge learners' comprehension. Examples include Curtin University's 'Research data management good practice self-assessment tool' (J. Chan et al., 2022) and The Carpentries pre- and post-training surveys (Jordan et al., 2018).

Complementary formative evaluation reviews training content and user experience and includes post-training feedback surveys and focus groups. Evaluating training provides an understanding of training delivery quality, and guides improvements in the learning experience (Kreber et al., 2001; Miller, 2017). Evaluation is best executed within a structured time range: throughout the training, immediately after training, 1-2 weeks after training, and three months after training (see [Figure 4](#)).

Training evaluation is designed to address these questions:

- Did the training achieve the intended outcomes?
- What needs to be changed for this training to be more effective?
- Is the content current?
- Were the delivery models/methods/platforms used appropriately?
- Does training frequency meet learner needs?
- Was the training pace suitable for learners?
- What knowledge or skills gaps need to be filled to enable training engagement?

Assessment and evaluation of training will:

- help determine if the training achieved its objectives,

- make training efficacy visible,
- identify learning gaps, and
- provide an opportunity to collect learning metrics that reflect trainer value.

Figure 4: Evaluation process and timeline.

Rule 8: Prepare for trainer turnover

Employee turnover may occur for a variety of reasons, including normal employee progression (promotion, resignation, re-assignment) and may be exacerbated by factors related to employment conditions, management, or benefits (Rivas & Jones, 2015).

The unpredictability of trainer turnover can lead to efforts being redirected towards the development and upskilling of new trainers. Turnover poses risks to the capacity to deliver quality SFT.

Increasing and maintaining trainer satisfaction can mitigate turnover. However, even well-designed and planned SFTs encounter trainer turnover, so succession planning is vital to ensure program sustainability (Samad et al., 2021, McGrath et al., 2019). Attendees' insights at the ARDC Digital Research Skills Summit 2023, resulted in the following strategies.

Strategies to increase trainer satisfaction

- Utilize professional training opportunities and determine if training activities count toward career progression.
- Recognize and foster the importance of the trainer's role.
- Invite contributions to the development of training materials, and recognize contributors.

Succession planning

- Call for volunteer trainers and provide appropriate rewards and recognition.
- Offer internships and mentoring.
- Build local or collaborative networks to coordinate specific types of training.
- Upskill existing trainers and pay them appropriately for the training they develop and deliver.
- Locate and use open source training materials to reduce the time and effort involved in developing training programs and refocus it towards delivery of the training.
- 'Train the trainer' sessions can benefit both existing and new trainers.

Many of these suggestions can be achieved by connecting with trainer communities ([Rule 4](#)).

Attendees at the ARDC Digital Research Skills Summit 2023 highlighted the necessity of systemic changes in the research workforce to professionalize instructor training and mitigate trainer turnover. Systemic changes require the identification, creation, and explicit recognition of training roles within the research community. This also entails normalizing the acknowledgment of training providers in research outputs, akin to acknowledging funding sources, editorial support, and other types of contributions.

Rule 9: Prepare to scale

What happens when training experiences high demand, trainers reach capacity, or organizations request replication of successful SFT? In these circumstances, you may need to scale. This entails growing the number of trainers and investing in other training modalities that support self-directed or peer learning.

Scaling involves first assessing training needs and determining the level of learner knowledge and discipline specificity. More niche or advanced skills training is likely not to need extensive scaling. Evaluation of an existing training offering will indicate whether scaling is needed ([Rule 7](#)).

Documentation, including the materials used for training and accompanying notes, is an excellent starting point to create resources for a larger audience, repeated deliveries, or self-directed learning (Schneider & McDonald, 2007). When identifying aspects that may be reused in later deliveries it is worth considering the format and methodology of training ([Rule 2](#)), the technology used ([Rule 5](#)), and even the layout of the room for an in-person event ([Figure 2](#)).

Ownership and intellectual property in training can affect the approach to scaling. It may be sufficient to simply allow trainers and learners to share and use training materials. This can be achieved by submitting them to an open access repository and applying an open reuse license for clarity of use and ease of citation. For consistency, it may be necessary to maintain oversight of who is delivering the material and to support their progress with scaling their delivery.

Designers of similar training can benefit from openly sharing training resources by working collaboratively to strengthen original material together, or pool efforts to produce a single new scaled-up training package combining their material. Providing opportunities for trainers to share experiences and to ask one another questions supports this. DReSA (Digital Research Skills Australasia, 2024b) is an example of an effective channel for encouraging and supporting collaborative efforts.

Finally, note that an institution or commercial organization branding an SFT has its organizational reputation to consider. This may influence the approach taken when scaling. In this situation, consult with the appropriate stakeholders regarding the level of documentation as there may be a need to ensure delivery of material is consistent with institutional guidelines and compliant with regulatory agencies (as required).

Rule 10: Recognise training spans careers

Training is not complete once the session has been delivered, and this is particularly true within the workforce. Career-spanning training is imperative to keep in line with current trends, and new techniques. At the ARDC Digital Research Skills Summit 2023, attendees identified the importance of recognizing a ‘vision for future success’ when upskilling researchers, as this will ultimately lead to supportive learning cultures and continuous uptake of necessary training.

Career-spanning training refers to the ongoing demand and need for specific professional development programs that effectively and incrementally improve an individual’s job performance over the course of a career. It is closely related to two similar concepts:

- **Lifelong learning** is a term used often by governments and policymakers to explicitly include learning for all purposes and contexts, including civic, social, and personal skills unrelated to employment (Aspin & Chapman, 2000).
- **Continuous Professional Development** is used in engineering, nursing, education and many other sectors to refer to ongoing professional learning activities often mandatory for maintaining professional registration or standing.

Throughout this article, we have provided tips to guide the development of SFT, which is one of the most effective methods of delivery due to its low cost, time commitment, and flexibility to adapt to unexpected changes (Williams et al., 2023). However, relevance, timeliness, duration, and many other factors influence a learner’s choices in the training they undertake. In addition to SFT, career-spanning training includes:

- **On-the-job training**, where skills are learned through hands-on experience while performing tasks within a role, often under the guidance of experienced colleagues or mentors.
- **Secondments** or temporary work assignments provide opportunities to gain new experiences, learn different skills, and contribute to projects outside their regular role.
- **Mentoring/coaching** can provide personalized guidance, support, and advice throughout a career, helping to navigate challenges, set goals, and make informed decisions.
- **Work-integrated learning**, also known as experiential learning, is an educational approach that integrates classroom learning with real-world work experiences.
- **Internships**, designed to provide real-world exposure to the working environment, allowing participants to apply theoretical learning and acquire new skills through practical tasks and projects.
- **Formal education**, such as a Bachelors, Masters or Doctoral degree in fields relevant to a career.

- **Micro-credentials** are short, focused learning programs offering specific skills or knowledge. They are more targeted than traditional degrees, often provided online by institutions or platforms, and can include badges, certificates, or digital credentials that can be showcased on resumes or profiles.
- **Study tours** are designed to enhance participants' understanding of a particular subject, concept, or industry. They are often aligned with the curriculum or learning objectives of a course.
- **A Community of Practice** is a group of individuals who come together with a shared interest, domain of knowledge, or professional focus to engage in collaborative learning, knowledge sharing, and skill development.

The responsibility for professional development and learning ultimately falls to the individual, and their self-efficacy (Likhomanov et al., 2020) and mindset (Yeager & Dweck, 2020). However, skills trainers, peak bodies, and employing organizations all play critical roles in supporting career-spanning training for researchers.

Willams et al (2023), have reiterated the importance of career-spanning training and identified a list of actions to strengthen its impact (see article for more information). In essence, the integration of learning throughout careers enables the collective workforce to rapidly adapt to cutting-edge technological changes and gives researchers opportunities to evolve their skills.

Conclusion

Based on constructive discussions with participants at the ARDC Digital Research Skills Summit 2023, SFT must be accessible, scalable, and sustainable. By incorporating the ten rules outlined in this article, research communities can cultivate effective skills training programs that empower researchers to continually enhance their capabilities. Through engaging with these guidelines, researchers can collectively build a culture of lifelong learning and skill development within the research community.

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